

Project acronym: SURE-Farm

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Duration: 4 years

D7.1. Webpage, project portal, social media accounts and co-creation platform

Work Performed by Partner 9, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

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Work Package	WP7
Task	T 7.2
Task lead	P9 leads this task together with P1, and small contributions from other partners
Dissemination level	Public

INDEX

1	The SURE-Farm webpage.....	3
1.1	Description.....	3
1.2	Plan of activities.....	4
2	The SURE-Farm portal.....	5
2.1	Description.....	5
2.2	Plan of activities.....	9
3	Social media accounts.....	9
3.1	Description.....	9
3.1	Plan of activities.....	11
4	Co-creation platform.....	12
4.1	Description.....	12
4.2	Plan of activities.....	12
4.3	Working Protocol.....	13

1 The SURE-Farm webpage

1.1 Description

The creation of the SURE-Farm website consists of the following steps:

- The **domain** of the SURE-Farm webpage is www.surefarmproject.eu.
- The **webpage hosting** is a Virtual Private Server (VPS) provided by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.
- The **design**: The web has a custom designed to ensure a fast content loading and an increased security. It is a Responsive Web Design (RWD) that allows desktop webpages to be viewed in response to the size of the screen or web browser used. The RWD ensures usability and satisfaction and perfect display on different devices (mobile, tablets and other devices).
- The **programming**: The web programming is wordpress (HTML5). The wordpress is an online, open source website creation tool written in PHP. It is easy to use and one of the most powerful website content management system (CMS). It allows to have a flexible website, facilitating to include every information as the project develops.

The main functionalities and characteristics of the SURE-Farm webpages are the following:

- The web site is in English.
- It provides links to:
 - The SURE-Farm intranet
 - The co-creation platform
 - Social media
- The structure of the contents of the web site is:
 1. HOME
 2. ABOUT
 - a. AT A GLANCE
 - b. THE CHALLENGE AND DIVERSE RESPONSE
 - c. THE PROJECT
 - d. CASES STUDIES
 - e. BENEFITS
 3. PARTNERS
 4. DELIVERABLES
 - a. PUBLIC DOCUMENTS
 - b. TOOLS
 - c. SCIENTIFIC SEMINARS

- 5. DIGITAL MATERIAL
- 6. NEWS AND EVENTS
- 7. CONTACT

The design and content of the website home is key to attract the attention and encourage visitors to browse the web through the different tabs.

The home page has the following elements:

On the top: There are the logo and the Intranet, Co-Creation platform and social media buttons. The tabs are horizontally displayed on capital letters.

In the middle, the body is divided into three parts:

1. First, the project's image with a picture and a catchy phrase. The picture and phrase are in motion.
2. Six boxes with direct access to key parts of the website: SURE-Farm at a glance, the co-creation platform, tweeter, release calendar, news and get involved.

On the bottom the logos of the partner are shown in movement by each four partners. The funding and contact of the project is detailed in the footer.

1.2 Plan of activities

Task/ Milestone	Month	Issue	WP—Lead beneficiary
MS32	M6	Website developed and operational, with operational co-creation platform	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	M2	SURE-Farm webpage domain and	WP7-P9 and P1

		VPS	
T7.2	M3	SURE-Farm webpage design	WP7- P9 and P1
T7.2	M3/M4	SURE-Farm programming	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	M6	Sure-Farm Website developed and operational	WP7-P9 and P1

2 The SURE-Farm portal

2.1 Description

We use the self-hosted file sync and share server, ownCloud to storage, access and share the documents, calendars and contacts of SURE-Farm through a web interface across devices. OwnCloud is the best option among the different providers analyzed (basecamp/innovation place/ zoho/Google suite /Microsoft 365). First, it is the most secure option because the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, manages and works with this cloud, so the documents will be stored directly by the university not by an external company. Should there be problems/doubts, it would be easier to solve them. Second, ownCloud provides similar functions than the rest of the platforms. And thirdly, ownCloud has the best price-quality ratio.

The functions that it provides are:

1. Store documents. We are able to define access to folder by user (reading access/full access)
2. Share and collaborate with anybody: Comments on files, tag them, and see the comments and tags by others.
3. Mobile and desktop syncing
4. Calendars and contacts
5. Activity feed and notifications
6. The UPM will be the administrator of the intranet and give full access to WU to manage the intranet. Any changes on the intranet users and access will be performed by the UPM.

The link to access to the intranet is :

<https://cloud9.cesvima.upm.es/index.php/login>

So far, 54 users have been added to the intranet by defining their user name, password and profile.

The structure of the intranet is detailed below:

- 1) Folder 1: Consortium
- 2) Folder 2: Templates
- 3) Folder 3: DOA
- 4) Folder 4 : Consortium Agreement
- 5) Folder 5 : Consortium Meetings (By year)
- 6) Folder 6 : Gran Agreement (Anex I.DOA)
- 7) Folder 7: Digital material
- 8) Folder 8: Reporting
- 9) Folder 9: Work Packages: We propose to organize the documents by WP and then by task
 - a) WP1
 - i) Task 1
 - ii) Task 2
 - iii) ---
 - b) WP2
 - c)
- 10) Folder 10: Dissemination for approval
- 11) Folder 11: Review Process
- 12) Folder 12 : Data Management
- 13) Folder 13 : Ethical Issues
- 14) Folder 14 : Logo

Some useful links have been shared with the SURE-Farm partners as well as the description of the principal ownCloud functionalities :

Useful links

Link to log in:

- <https://cloud9.cesvima.upm.es/index.php/login>

To synchronize the ownCloud documents (desktop or mobile):

- <https://owncloud.org/install> / Second option (Sync your data)

To synchronize the ownCloud calendar and contacts:

- Outlook: <https://nextcloud.com/blog/nextcloud-offers-caldav-synchronizer-for-outlook-users/>

- MAC : https://doc.owncloud.org/server/9.0/user_manual/pim/sync_osx.html
- iphone/ipad: https://doc.owncloud.org/server/9.0/user_manual/pim/sync_ios.html
- Android: <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.deependhulla.opensync>

Main functionalities:

1. Define the profile

2. Store and share SURE-Farm documents

3. Share and collaborate with anybody: We can add comments on files, tag them, and see the comments and tags by others.

4. Sharing calendars and contacts. Activity feed and notification

The SURE-Farm partners have a detailed ownCloud manual uploaded to the SURE-Farm intranet.

2.2 Plan of activities

Task	Month	Issue	WP–Lead beneficiary
T7.2	M2	SURE-Farm portal design	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	M2	SURE-Farm portal operational	WP7- P9 and P1

3 Social media accounts

3.1 Description

Four social media accounts have been created and designed:

1.- Twitter: @surefarmproject

2.- Facebook: @surefarmproject

3.- LinkedIn: SURE-Farm

4.- Instagram: SURE-Farm

3.1 Plan of activities

Task/Milestone	Month	Issue	WP–Lead beneficiary
MS30	M2	Measures of social media penetration developed	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	M3	SURE-Farm social media created	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	As soon as the webpage is operational (M6)	Project and results communication through the social media	WP7- P9 and P1

4 Co-creation platform

4.1 Description

One of the aims of the WP7 is to ensure that a wide range of stakeholders engage actively in SURE-Farm project through the co-creation process. Three different ways have been identify to facilitate the transversal involvement of the stakeholders throughout the project: 1) The co-creation platform, 2) the local co-creation workshops; and 3) the central co-creation meetings.

The co-creation platform is a virtual platform through which the co-creation members actively participate in the process of achieving the following aims:

- Design of improved Risk Management tools (WP2. Risk management)
- Design of policy improvements (WP4. Policies, WP5. Impact Assessment)
- Design of roadmaps for implementation (WP6. Enabling environment)

The co-creation platform will be operational from M10 to M48.

4.2 Plan of activities

Task/ Milestone	Month	Issue	WP–Lead beneficiary
MS32	M6	Website developed and operational, with operational co-creation platform	WP7-P9 and P1
Task	Month	Issue	WP–Lead beneficiary
T7.2	M1	Co-creation platform objectives	WP7-P9 and P1
T7.2	M3	Contact with co-creation experts	WP7- P9 and P1
T7.2	M4	Definition of the scope, functionalities and characteristics of the Co-creation platform: members, activities, timeline, monitoring and results reports.	WP7- P9 and P1
T7.2	M10	Operational co-creation platform	WP7- P9 and P1

The due date of the co-creation platform has been delayed form M6 to M10. The objectives, scope, instruments and users need to be previously discuss and approved in the quick-off meeting, 28th – 29th of September 2017.

4.3 Working Protocol

The digital co-creation is a cross-cutting work item in SURE-Farm. The results generated in the digital platform feed into different WPs in the project and vice versa. It is required the coordination of the partners involved in the different WPs to ensure that the progresses of the project and the platform keep the same pace.

Three working groups will be created according to the three main goals of the digital co-creation platform: 1) Risk Management Tools (RMT) Group; 2) Policy and FopIA team; 3) Implementation roadmaps team. In order to better organize the activity in the platform, the teams will be working sequentially:

1. RMT Group
2. Policy and FoPIA Group
3. Roadmaps Group

In order to facilitate the joint work, the following actions will be carried out:

- Creation of google groups to facilitate the e-mail communication
- Organize skype meetings: 2-3 per month depending on the progresses.
- Share documents in a specific folder “Digital Co-creation Platform” in the intranet. A sub-folder will be created by each group.

